

Green synthesis and characterisation of spherical and rod shaped CuO nanostructures using Carica papaya: Antimicrobial potential against oral biofilms and haemolytic assessment – An in-vitro study

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Abstract

Background: Copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs) have broad-spectrum antimicrobial properties and hemocompatibility. Conventional synthesis methods, however, often involve toxic reagents and environmentally hazardous processes. *Carica papaya*, rich in polyphenols, flavonoids and have phytochemical-mediated reducing and stabilizing capabilities. Green synthesis approaches utilizing plant extracts show better biocompatibility, cost-effectiveness, and ecological safety.

Objective: This study aims to green synthesize spherical and rod-shaped CuO nanostructures using *Carica papaya* leaf extract and evaluate their physicochemical, antimicrobial, and hemolytic properties.

Methods: CuO NPs and nanorods (NRs) were synthesized using aqueous *Carica papaya* leaf extract. Characterization of the herbal extract was done using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* was assessed using agar well diffusion. Hemolytic potential was determined using human blood samples.

Results: XRD revealed crystalline CuO NPs (30.86 nm) and NRs (38.92 nm). SEM showed spherical particles and nanorods of ~60–80 nm width and 700–800 nm length. Antimicrobial studies demonstrated superior inhibition of *S. aureus* (>15 mm) compared to *E. coli* (15 mm). Hemolysis remained below 1% up to 50 µg/mL, confirming good hemocompatibility.

Conclusion: Green synthesized CuO nanostructures show potential for biomedical applications due to their biocompatibility and effective antibacterial properties. Future studies may explore their antioxidant and anticancer effects.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, *Carica papaya*, Copper oxide nanoparticles, Green synthesis, Hemocompatibility, Nanorods

Introduction

Nanotechnology continues to revolutionize biomedical research, with metal oxide nanoparticles gaining prominence due to their multifunctional properties like biological, physical, electronic, mechanical, magnetic, thermal and chemical properties (1)(2).(3) Copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs) have drawn significant attention for their wide band gap (~1.7 eV), high stability, and broad-spectrum biological activities including antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anticancer potentials (4,5). CuO was a p-type semiconductor with established applications in catalysis, energy storage, and more recently, medicine (6). Green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles utilises the plant's natural phytochemistry to yield biocompatible, functional nanomaterials in an eco-friendly way (7). Unlike conventional physical or chemical routes which use high-temperature decomposition, strong-reducing agents consume more energy and often use hazardous reagents (8). Green synthesis techniques were economical, eco-friendly, and biocompatible.

Carica papaya, a tropical plant with a high phytochemical content and potential for therapeutic use and biosynthesis of nanoparticles (9). The aqueous extract of *C. papaya* leaves is rich in polyphenols, flavonoids, alkaloids like carpaine and other antioxidants that can reduce Cu^{2+} to CuO thereby aiding in reduction and stabilization of CuO nanostructures (10,11). The biogenic CuO particles were more stable and biocompatible than those made with toxic chemicals. Studies report that green-synthesized CuO particles showed enhanced biological properties, stronger antibacterial and anticancer effects than chemically synthesized CuO NPs (12).

In this study, spherical and rod-shaped CuO nanostructures were synthesised using *Carica papaya* leaf extract and characterized them using FTIR, XRD, and SEM techniques. We also investigated their anti microbial activity against *E. coli*, in vitro hemolysis tests to assess hemocompatibility between *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. To demonstrate the potential biomedical utility of nanoparticles by correlating their morphology with biological performance.

Materials and Methods

Green Synthesis of CuO NPs and CuO Nanorods

The biosynthesis of CuO NPs and copper oxide nanorods (CuO NRs) was performed using *Carica papaya* leaf extract as a green reducing and stabilizing agent. Fresh leaves were collected from residential gardens in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. After thorough washing, the leaves were shade-dried, powdered, and boiled with distilled water to prepare the aqueous extract. The extract was then filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and stored at 4°C for further synthesis.

To synthesize CuO nanostructures, a copper precursor (copper nitrate) was mixed with the prepared extract under continuous stirring. Reaction conditions, such as temperature (maintained at 80°C) and duration (48 hours), were optimized to influence morphology. Spherical CuO NPs and rod-shaped CuO NRs were generated by adjusting extract concentration and reaction time. Post-reaction, the colloidal solutions were centrifuged, washed thrice with deionized water and ethanol, and dried to obtain solid CuO nanostructures.

Physicochemical Characterization

The crystalline structure and average crystallite size of the CuO NPs and CuO NRs were evaluated using XRD. The Scherrer formula was applied to estimate average particle size based on full-width half-maximum (FWHM) of the diffraction peaks. FTIR analysis was carried out to identify surface functional groups associated with bioactive phytochemicals that played a role in reduction and stabilization. The CuO NPs showed major peaks at 1045 cm^{-1} , while CuO NRs exhibited peaks at 1427 cm^{-1} , corresponding to CuO vibrations and polyphenolic capping agents. SEM imaging revealed the morphology and surface features of CuO nanostructures. The CuO NPs were spherical with diameters ranging from 60–80 nm. The CuO NRs had widths of 60–80 nm and lengths ranging from 700–800 nm.

Agar well diffusion method was used to culture *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive) on nutrient agar plates. Two bacterial strains, *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive), were cultured on nutrient agar plates wells were punched into the agar and filled with CuO NPs or CuO NRs suspended in PBS at different concentrations (10, 25, 50, 75, 100, and 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Zones of inhibition were assessed after 24 hours of incubation at 37°C. Each test was performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility.

The hemocompatibility of CuO NPs and CuO NRs was evaluated using human blood obtained from a healthy volunteer. The collected blood was anticoagulated with 3.2% trisodium citrate and diluted in a 1:10 ratio with PBS. CuO NPs and CuO NRs were prepared in PBS at six concentrations (10, 25, 50, 75, 100, and 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and incubated with diluted blood at 37°C for 2 hours. Samples were centrifuged, and the absorbance of the supernatant was recorded at 540 nm

to quantify released hemoglobin. Hemolysis % was calculated against positive (distilled water) and negative (PBS) controls.

Results

Physicochemical Characterization

XRD patterns confirmed the formation of crystalline monoclinic phase CuO. CuO NPs exhibited a smaller average crystallite size of 30.86 nm, whereas CuO NRs showed slightly larger dimensions at 38.92 nm. The distinct diffraction peaks at 2θ values matched standard CuO phase patterns, confirming phase purity (Figure 1).

FTIR spectra revealed peaks at 1045 cm^{-1} for CuO NPs and at 1427 cm^{-1} for CuO NRs. These correspond to Cu–O stretching vibrations and interactions with –OH and C–O groups, suggesting effective capping by biomolecules present in *Carica papaya* extract. The presence of such functional groups indicates the role of phytochemicals in reducing copper ions and stabilizing the resulting nanoparticles (Figure 2). SEM analysis showed morphological differences between the two nanostructures, Spherical nanoparticles with uniform morphology and a size range of 60–80 nm. Rod-shaped structures with consistent widths (~60–80 nm) and elongated lengths of 700–800 nm, indicating successful anisotropic growth possibly influenced by extract composition and concentration (Figure 3).

Antimicrobial Activity

The zone of inhibition was more prominent in CuO NRs compared to CuO NPs at all concentrations. For CuO NRs, the zone of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* exceeded 15 mm, while for *E. coli* it remained around 15 mm at $200\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$. CuO NPs showed comparatively lower zones of inhibition against both organisms, with inhibition zones increasing proportionally with concentration. The enhanced efficacy of NRs may be attributed to their increased surface contact with bacterial membranes and possible mechanical penetration, especially in Gram-positive organisms (Figure 4).

Hemolytic Assay

CuO NPs and CuO NRs demonstrated excellent hemocompatibility. At concentrations up to $50\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$, both nanostructures exhibited less than 1% hemolysis, which falls well within the safe limits of biomaterial compatibility. At higher concentrations ($75\text{--}200\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$), a mild increase in hemolysis was observed, more pronounced in NRs, likely due to their higher aspect ratio and surface reactivity. These results indicate that both nanostructures were nontoxic to blood cells at therapeutic doses (Figure 5).

Discussion

The present study demonstrated a green synthesis of both spherical CuO NPs and rod-shaped CuO NRs using aqueous *Carica papaya* leaf extract as a natural reducing agent with biocompatibility and antimicrobial properties (13). The use of *C. papaya*, a medicinally significant plant rich in phytochemicals like polyphenols and flavonoids, provided a biogenic platform conducive for nanoparticle formation (14).

Characterization through FTIR confirmed the presence of functional groups consistent with Cu–O bonds at 1045 cm^{-1} and 1427 cm^{-1} , which were similar to those reported in earlier green synthesis studies involving CuO NPs from *Carica papaya* leaves and peels(15). XRD analysis revealed monoclinic phase CuO with average crystallite sizes of 30.86 nm (spherical) and 38.92 nm (rod-shaped), aligning well with previous reports where biogenic CuO particles typically ranged from 20–40 nm.

The SEM images revealed morphological differences dictated by synthesis parameters, particularly reaction time and temperature. CuO NRs formed at 80°C for 48 hours displayed lengths ranging from 700–800 nm and widths between 60–80 nm. These dimensions and aspect ratios were critical in defining the surface area and cellular interaction dynamics, particularly relevant in antimicrobial and blood-contact applications (16).

The inhibitory zone of the biosynthetic CuO NRs was higher in the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* ($>15\text{ mm}$) than in the presence of *Escherichia coli* ($>15\text{ mm}$). The morphology-dependent antibacterial activity was likely due to the high aspect ratio of nanorods, which facilitates penetration into bacterial membranes and compromises cell integrity, thereby promote the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) leads to oxidative stress-induced bacterial death ((17),(18,19,20)

Both CuO NPs and NRs showed less than 1% hemolysis up to $50\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$, according to hemolytic analysis, indicating good blood compatibility. Hemolysis was found to slightly increase at higher concentrations, especially with NRs as the increased surface contact and possible production of ROS, which damages erythrocyte membranes oxidatively. The significance of ROS in CuO-induced cytotoxicity and nanoparticle shape were highlighted by this concentration-dependent hemolytic behavior.(21)(22). However, the haemolysis values for these nanostructures remained well below the ASTM F756-00 limit for non-hemolytic materials, which supports their safety profile.(23)

The findings show that the structural characteristics of CuO NRs contribute to their superior functional properties but also dose optimization in therapeutic formulations. The biocompatibility and potent antimicrobial activity suggest promising applications in wound dressings, dental

materials, and targeted drug delivery systems. However, further in vivo studies and long-term toxicity evaluations were essential to validate these applications in clinical settings.

Conclusion

This study shows the green synthesis of CuO NPs and CuO NRs using the extract of the *Carica papaya* leaf to synthesise nanoparticles with the physicochemical and biomedical properties. CuO NRs have been demonstrated to have increased antibacterial activity, especially against *Staphylococcus aureus*, because of their enhanced surface interactions and generation of ROS and with minimal hemolytic activity displayed by both CuO NPs and CuO NRs. All these results demonstrate the potential of Papaya-derived copper nanostructures which were biocompatible and environmentally friendly for antimicrobial applications.

General Experimental Section

Green Synthesis of CuO NPs and CuO Nanorods

The biosynthesis of CuO NPs and copper oxide nanorods (CuO NRs) was performed using *Carica papaya* leaf extract. Fresh leaves were collected from residential gardens in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. After thorough washing, the leaves were shade-dried, powdered, and boiled with distilled water to prepare the aqueous extract. The extract was then filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and stored at 4°C for further synthesis.

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Declarations

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Conflict of Interest Statement:

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to this study.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee SRB SDC/OPATH-2302/25/095

Consent to Participate

Informed written consent was obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study.

Consent to Publish

Not applicable. The manuscript does not contain any individual person's data in an identifiable form.

Authors' Contributions

Pravallika Kakada and Dinesh Yasothkumar had conceptualized and designed the study. Both the authors had contributed to data collection and laboratory analysis and performed data analysis and interpretation. All authors critically reviewed the manuscript and approved the final version.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Availability of Data and Materials

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Figures

Figure 1 : X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Patterns of CuO NPs

Figure 2: FTIR Spectrum of CuO

Figure 3: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Images of CuO Nanoparticles (NPs) and Nanorods (NRs)

Figure 4: Antimicrobial Activity of CuO Nanoparticles and Nanorods Against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

Figure 5- Hemolysis Assay of CuO Nanorods (NRs) and Nanoparticles (NPs)

Figure Legends

Figure 1 : X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Patterns of CuO NPs

The XRD patterns of CuO NS (red) and CuO NR (black) were shown. Both samples exhibit characteristic diffraction peaks consistent with the monoclinic phase of CuO, indicating high crystallinity.

Figure 2: FTIR Spectrum of CuO NP's, Peaks observed at around $520\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to Cu–O stretching vibrations. Other signals, such as those near $1400\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 3300 cm^{-1} .

Figure 3: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Images of CuO Nanoparticles (NPs) and Nanorods (NRs)

SEM micrographs showing morphological characteristics of CuO nanostructures synthesized via green synthesis.(a) and (b): CuO nanoparticles (NPs) at different magnifications, exhibiting aggregated spherical morphology with relatively uniform particle distribution.(c) and (d): CuO nanorods (NRs), displaying elongated rod-like structures with varying aspect ratios, confirming successful anisotropic growth.

Figure 4: Antimicrobial Activity of CuO Nanoparticles and Nanorods Against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

Zone of inhibition (mm) measured for different concentrations (10–100 mg/mL) of CuO nanostructures against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* using agar well diffusion assay. CuO NPs exhibit dose-dependent antibacterial activity, with greater inhibition zones observed for *E. coli* compared to *S. aureus*. CuO NRs demonstrate enhanced antimicrobial efficacy at higher concentrations, with consistent inhibition for both bacterial strains.

Figure 5- Hemolysis Assay of CuO Nanorods (NRs) and Nanoparticles (NPs)

Bar graph showing percentage hemolysis induced by CuO NRs and NPs at varying concentrations (10–200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). CuO NRs show marginally higher hemolysis compared to NPs at elevated concentrations.